

Evaluation of the inhibitory potential of *Acacia nilotica* bioactive compounds against *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* using molecular docking

M. M. Shehu^{1*}, J. Umar², and A. M. Lawal³

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty Science, Federal University Gashua, Yobe State Nigeria

²Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty Science, Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, Faculty Science, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Correspondence: muhammadmansur56@yahoo.com; +2347039072260

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Abstract

African trypanosomiasis remains a major public challenge in sub-Saharan Africa, compounded by the emergence of drug-resistant *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* strain. In this study, molecular docking modelling was used to determine the anti-trypanosomal inhibitory effect of *Acacia nilotica*. The molecular docking was carried out through AutoDock Vina in open-source Python Prescription 0.8. Twenty-five (25) compounds were identified as potential candidates and analyzed (in silico) for their drug likeness from the rules of Lipinski, Egan, and Veber through the Swiss Adme server. The 3D conformers of drug-like compounds were uploaded in Python prescription suit (PyRx) and optimized via Open babel in PyRx (version 0.8). The anti-trypanosomal activity of these compounds was investigated using a molecular docking assay against two proteins from *T. brucei brucei*, namely arginine kinase 3 (Accession No. EAN76668.1) and trans-sialidase (AlphaFold ID: AF-Q57YTZ-F1). The returned binding energy (kcal/mol) suggested five suitable candidates: Epicatechin (-6.2 and -7.9 kcal/mol), Kaempferol (-5.9 and -7.2 kcal/mol), Taxifolin (-6.2 and -7.9 kcal/mol), 1-acetyl-beta carboline (-5.9 and -6.9 kcal/mol), and 3,4,7-trimethylquercetin (-5.7 and -7.4 kcal/mol). In conclusion, the drug-like compounds of *A. nilotica* demonstrated favourable binding energies (kcal/mol). With five biomolecule showing effective interaction with the enzyme active site. According to the druglike compounds of *A. nilotica*'s returning binding energy (kcal/mol), the five appropriate biomolecules in this investigation bind effectively to the two enzymes' active sites. Due to its greater accessibility, more research is necessary to evaluate *A. nilotica* in vitro or in vivo to determine whether it might be employed as a less costly and effective medication.

Keywords: *Acacia nilotica*, Molecular docking, Trypanosomiasis, *Trypanosoma brucei brucei*.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The protozoan that causes trypanosomiasis in humans as well as vertebrate animals is called a trypanosome. Mostly found in Sub-Saharan Africa, these extracellular flagellates belong to the genus *Trypanosoma* [1;2]. Animal trypanosomiasis, sometimes called nagana in cattle and horses, is caused by African trypanosomiasis, which is commonly referred to as sleeping sickness in humans [3]. Previous studies have identified three subspecies of *T. brucei*: *T. b. brucei*, *T. b. gambiense*, and *T. b. rhodesiense*. Trypanocides are important in the care of African animal

trypanosomiasis, their usage is limited by their toxicity, lack of effectiveness, expense, and route of administration compared to traditional remedies. This suggests that trypanocides are not given much priority in the global health management of African trypanosomiasis. Additionally, the phenomenon of medication resistance poses a threat to the positive therapeutic outcome [4]. The effective use of trypanocides in the field, medication resistance, and inexpensive AAT diagnostics are among the areas with gaps in knowledge and resources [5]. There is an urgent need for new medications to treat African trypanosomiasis because some of the current

medications have dangerous side effects that can be lethal due to their toxicity [4]

Acacia nilotica is widely distributed throughout western Africa, especially in Nigeria. It is a noteworthy ornamental, therapeutic species and has numerous biological activities, including anti-tuberculosis, anti-leprosy, and anti-diarrheal properties. Additionally, it has been discovered to include a variety of naturally occurring active compounds that could be utilized to develop novel therapeutic targets [6]. In many rural Nigerian villages, traditional healers use pieces of numerous African plants to treat blood parasite illnesses, such as trypanosomiasis [7]. This study is intended to evaluate the inhibitory potentials of bioactive compounds from *Acacia nilotica* against *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* using molecular docking.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Selection and Retrieval of Protein sequences

Two proteins from *T. brucei brucei* namely; Arginine kinase 3 (Accession No. EAN76668.1) and Trans-Sialidase (AlphaFold ID: AF-Q57YTZ-F1) were selected. No structures of these proteins in protein databases so we opted for their protein sequences from the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) server (National Center for Biotechnology Information (nih.gov)) and alphaFold's DeepMind of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) server (AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (ebi.ac.uk)).

2.2 Homology Modelling and Protein Structure for Molecular Docking

The acquired protein sequences of Arginine kinase 3 (Accession No. EAN76668.1) and Trans-Sialidase (AlphaFold ID: AF-Q57YTZ-F1) were uploaded into the workspace module of SWISS-MODEL server (<https://swissmodel.expasy.org>), to build their 3D structures. Afterwards, the Protein structures were prepared for docking and minimized using the relevant tools in UCSF-Chimera© (version 1.13) software (<http://www.cgl.ucsf.edu/chimera>) [8].

2.3 Selection, Drug likeness screening, Retrieval and Optimization of Ligands

Twenty five (25) plant compounds were selected from *Acacia nilotica* [9; 10] through extensive

literature mining. All plant compounds were *in silico*-wise analyzed for their drug likeness from the rules of Lipinski [11], Egan [12], and Veber [13] through the SwissADME server (SwissADME). Those compounds that scaled through the screening were obtained from a daughter webserver of NCBI called PubChem in structure data file (SDF) (PubChem (nih.gov)). The 3D conformers of drug-like compounds were uploaded in Python prescription suit (PyRx) and optimized via Open babel in PyRx (version 0.8) which converted the ligands energetically to the most stable structures using merck molecular force field 94 (MMFF94).

2.4 Molecular docking simulation

The molecular docking was carried out through AutoDock Vina in open-source Python Prescription 0.8 [14] to acquire possible binding orientations and binding energy (BE) of compounds at the selected binding domain of arginine kinase 3 and trans-sialidase. This region was covered with the aid of the grid box with dimensions (17.5878 x 21.5384 x 27.7438) Å and (26.7771 x 17.0536 x 21.5627) Å, and the centers was adjusted based on the site of binding in arginine kinase 3 and trans-sialidase respectively. The area in arginine kinase 3 was predicted using dog site scorer module [15] of protein-plus server (<https://proteins.plus>) and was predicted to comprise of Leu48, Asp74, Val74, Ile76, Gln77, Ser78, Gly79, Ser85, Gly86, Val87, Gly88, Leu89, Tyr90, Ala91, Pro92, Phe104, Val107, Ile108, Tyr111, His112, Pro160, Phe216, Ala219, Ala220, Phe292, Cys293, Pro294, Ser295 and Leu297. That of trans-sialidase binding site was reported to compose of Arg374, Arg298, Arg84, Asp146 and Arg102 [16]. After the docking run, compounds with the least binding energy were subjected to molecular visualization in order to analyze their binding poses (3D) and molecular interaction fingerprints (2D) through PyMOL© Molecular Graphics (version 2.4, 2016, Schrödinger LLC) (Seeliger and Groot, 2010) and LigPlot⁺ software [17] respectively.

3.0 Results

3.1 Homology Modeling of Protein Structures

The 3D structure of the protein in the parasite of interest had not been crystallized and deposited in the popular RCSB protein database. Thus, a homology modeling approach was used to build a suitable protein structure for this study. After creating the two structures, the assessment of the

models showed that the modeled arginine kinase 3 from that of *T. b. brucei* had 81.69% identity and 95.44 % of its amino acid residues found in the favored region. This was also observed with transglutaminase modeled from a template from alpha fold's

deep mind server with 92.63 % of its amino acid residues and identity of 100 % (Figure 4.1). These showed that both structures are useful for molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations.

Figure 1: Homology modelled Protein structures' assessment. Ramachandran plots of a) AK 3 and b) TS. According to this plot, most of the amino acid residues were seen to occupy the favored regions. Multiple sequence alignments of c) AK 3 and d) TS against their templates from 2J1Q and AF-Q57YTZ-F1 with sequence identities of 81.69 % and 100% respectively.

3.2 Drug Likeness Screening

The outcome of the screening of compounds evaluated in silico against the two enzymes of *T. brucei* brucei showed that 25 compounds from

Acacia nilotica could be drug-like after passing them through Lipinski's, Egan's, and Veber's rules, oral bioavailability inclusive as presented in the table below

Table 3.1: Drug likeness screening of compounds in *A. nilotica* using Swiss Adme server

Molecule	PubChem ID	Lipinski #violations	Veber #violations	Egan #violations	Bioavailability Score
1,3,4 eugenol	3314	0	0	0	0.55
1,8,11-Heptadecatriene, (Z, Z)	5352709	0	0	0	0.55
1-acetyl-beta carboline	638667	0	0	0	0.55
2-methylresorcinol acetate	23469416	0	0	0	0.55
3,4,7-trimethylquercetin	5748558	0	0	0	0.55
2-Nitro-3-picoline	564205	0	0	0	0.55
4-methylbenzenethiol	7811	0	0	0	0.55
4-O- methylmannose	345716	0	0	0	0.55
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid	3931	1	1	1	0.85
9-Octadecenamide	1930	1	1	0	0.55
14,17-Octadecadienoic acid	78383942	1	1	1	0.85
15-Hydroxypentadecanoic acid	78360	0	1	0	0.85

arachidonic acid	444899	0	1	0	0.85
D-Glucuronic acid	88785	0	0	0	0.55
Ergost-5-en-3-ol	18660356	1	0	1	0.55
Ergosta-5,22-dien-3-ol	54152120	1	0	1	0.55
Gallic acid	370	0	0	0	0.56
Epicatechin	72276	0	0	0	0.55
Taxifolin	439533	0	0	0	0.55
Vitexin	5280441	1	1	1	0.55
Epicatechin-5-gallate	70697735	1	1	1	0.55
Ethyl gallate	13250	0	0	0	0.55
m-Digallic acid	341	1	1	1	0.11
Kaempferol	5280863	0	0	0	0.55
Myricetin	5281672	1	1	1	0.55

4.2.3. Molecular Docking Analysis

To give an insight into the potential of *Acacia nilotica* against infections caused by *T. brucei brucei*, we subjected the compounds of these plants that were predicted to be druglike to molecular docking against two protein targets (AK 3 and TS) that are valuable to the pathology of animal

trypanosome infection. This study indicates that druglike compounds in *Acacia nilotica* are good binders to the active site of both proteins, indicated by the returned binding energy (kcal/mol) (Tables 3.2). The lower the binding energy, the likelihood is the affinity of compounds to the active site of the targeted proteins in *T. brucei brucei*.

Table 3.2: Binding energy (kcal/mol) of drug-like compounds from *Acacia nilotica* docked against *T. b. brucei*'s arginine kinase 3 and Trans-Sialidase enzymes using auto dock vina

Molecule	PubChem ID	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)	
		Arginine Kinase 3	Trans-sialidase
1,3,4 eugenol	3314	-4.7	-5.4
1,8,11-Heptadecatriene, (Z,Z)	5352709	-4.3	-5.2
1-acetyl-beta carboline	638667	-5.9	-6.9
2-methylresorcinol acetate	23469416	-5.0	-5.3
3,4,7-trimethylquercetin	5748558	-5.3	-7.4
2-Nitro-3-picoline	564205	-4.9	-4.9
4-methylbenzenethiol	7811	-4.2	-4.1
4-O- methylmannose	345716	-5.0	-5.9
15-Hydroxypentadecanoic acid	78360	-4.1	-5.1
arachidonic acid	444899	-5.8	-5.9
D-Glucuronic acid	88785	-5.1	-5.9
Gallic acid	370	-4.8	-4.8
Epicatechin	72276	-6.2	-7.6
Taxifolin	439533	-6.2	-7.9
Ethyl gallate	13250	-5.0	-6.2
Kaempferol	5280863	-5.9	-7.2

4.0 Discussion

The present studies indicate that druglike compounds in *A. nilotica* are good binders to the active sites of both proteins, indicated by the returned binding energy (kcal/mol). The lower the binding energy, the likelihood is the affinity of compounds to the active site of the targeted proteins in *T. brucei brucei*. This finding supports the work of [18] Vázquez-Jiménez *et al.* [18] who earlier detected 487 compounds derived from benzoic acid as potential arginine kinase 3 and trans-sialidase inhibitors with a more promising binding energy value (< -7.7 kcal/mol) than the known inhibitor 2,3-dehydro-2-deoxy-N-acetylneuraminic acid. According to Pereira [19], arginine kinase 3 plays a pivotal role in energy metabolism by catalyzing the transfer of phosphate groups, essential for ATP production in *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* and is one of the key enzymes, responsible for the parasites' metabolic plasticity. Valera-Vera *et al.* [20] reports that through molecular docking simulation, some plant-derived polyphenolic pigments, such as anthocyanidins, were predicted to inhibit arginine kinase 3, it exhibits favorable binding interactions by targeting this enzyme, the compounds disrupt ATP synthesis, thereby impeding the parasite's energy production and ultimately compromising its survival. Boniface *et al.* [21] and Orosco *et al.* [22] earlier notes that trans-sialidase is critical enzyme in *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* involved in host-parasite interactions and immune evasion and its Inhibition could hinder the parasite's ability to modulate host immune responses, thus attenuating its virulence and aiding in host clearance of the infection.

It is noteworthy that neither of the compounds from *A. nilotica* violated any of the drug-likeness guidelines (Veber, Egan, or Lipinski), which makes them great candidates for further drug development. This observation has been supported by numerous studies from different plant metabolites in molecular docking investigations [7; 21;22].

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that bioactive compounds from *Acacia nilotica* exhibit significant in silico inhibitory potentials against resistant strain of *Trypanosoma brucei brucei*. Molecular docking analysis revealed favourable binding affinities and

interactions with key parasites targets, underscoring the therapeutic promise of these phytochemicals as potential lead compounds for novel anti-trypanosomal drugs development. This finding provides computational basis for consideration of *A. nilotica*-derived molecules in the management of drugs-resistant trypanosomiasis.

Recommendation

Further experimental validation is essential to substantiate the computational predictions. In vitro assay against *T. b. brucei* should be conducted to confirm inhibitory activities, followed by in vivo studies to assess the pharmacological efficacy, safety and pharmacokinetics profiles. Structural optimization and molecular dynamic s simulations are recommended to refine ligand-target interactions and enhance drug-likeness. Additionally, synergistic evaluation with existing trypanosidal agents may provide novel therapeutic strategies for overcoming resistance.

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